

doi:10.5281/zenodo.16569055

Remote Sensing Capabilities And Gully Erosion Studies

*Aniebone, V.O. PhD., Yusuf, A.K., Garba, I. & Samuel, J.E

Nigerian Institute for Oceanography and Marine Research, Lagos

*Corresponding author: Aniebone Victor Obiora. Email: aniebonevic@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Gully erosion is a consequent of exogenic movements and is a type of erosion that occurs when water flows over the surface of the ground and causes a channel or groove to form. The erosion problems of an area are subject to certain factors which include the geology, land use act, geomorphology, climate, soil texture, and nature of bio diversity of the area. The growing interest in studying gully erosion, its impacts and controlling factors that vary under a wide range of causes has led to the development of numerous stochastic and process-based models, with increasing emphasis on the use of the Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Satellite Remote Sensing (SRS). Remote sensing technology is massively deployed in the study of natural hazards of which gully erosion is part of them. Remote sensing technologies do operate within certain electromagnetic spectrums or spectral bands and the study looked at the various spectrums/bands and their capabilities in natural hazards studies with particular reference to gully erosion. Remote sensing exhibits various capabilities with respect to data acquisition such as wide area coverage, high spatial resolution, frequent data acquisition, cost effectiveness, and ability to access remote or inaccessible areas. The remote sensing technologies used in gully hazard applications are grouped into four and these are: synthetic aperture radar sensors, optical and infrared sensors, high resolution sensors and microwave sensors. The study looked at the satellites/sensors applications and their characteristics such as electromagnetic spectrum covered (band), spatial resolutions, year of satellite launch, revisit time, life span, orbit and limitations/disadvantages.

Keywords: Remote sensing, satellite/sensor types, characteristics, gully erosion studies

INTRODUCTION.

In recent years natural hazards - many of those of geologic origin - became an issue of increasing public awareness. In earth geology/geomorphology we identify two major forces that influence the surface of our planet. They are the endogenic and exogenic forces. Both can result in disasters. The endogenic forces, stemming from the earth's interior, can cause uplifting, earthquakes, as well as volcanic activity. Among the hazards from the exogenic forces are erosion, flooding, desertification with all the associated disasters once larger populations are affected. All the processes mentioned here can develop into catastrophic events in the case, the population is not prepared. Often the impact of the event is underestimated, or the event develops more rapidly than expected.

Soil erosion is a worldwide phenomenon which ravages large areas of land particularly in high rainfall or windy locations. It has been documented from the earliest of times as severe environmental hazard (Jstor, 1996., Poesen et al., 1996 and Kakembo et al., 2010). The erosion problems of an area are subject to certain factors which include the geology, land use act, geomorphology, climate, soil texture, and nature

of bio diversity of the area. Gully erosion is a consequent of exogenic movements and is a type of erosion that occurs when water flows over the surface of the ground and causes a channel or groove to form. It is a common problem in many parts of the world, particularly in areas with heavy rainfall, steep slopes, and poor land management practices. Gully erosion is a highly visible form of soil erosion or an antecedent of the removal of soil by running water that affects soil productivity, restricts land use and can threaten roads, fences and buildings. According to Feliciano (2008), gully erosion is an incised cut step - sided channel, with an eroding head cut and slumping sidewalls. Gully itself is a relatively deep vertical walled channel recently formed within alley where no well-defined channel previously existed (Beths, 1993). These develop because of a decrease in the erosion resistance of the land surface or increase in the erosion forces acting on the land surface. As water channeled across unprotected land, it washes away the soil along the drainage lines.

Recent estimates suggest that about seven per cent (7%) of the world's topsoil is lost yearly to erosion. The World Resources Institute claims that Burkina Faso loses 25 tonnes of soil per hectare per year, Ethiopia loses 42 tonnes, Nepal loses 70 tonnes, Decan Plateau (India) loses 100 tonnes, and Loess Plateau of North China loses 251 tonnes respectively (Kalu, 1995). Also, the soil survey of England and Wales reported that 44 per cent of arable soils in the United Kingdom, an area once considered not to be under threat, are now at risk. It has also been estimated that 20 million hectares of agriculturally usable land worldwide is lost to erosion annually (Poesen et al. 1996).

In Nigeria, the problem of gully erosion has formed a subject for serious consideration since the early 1920s, it has continued to attract wider attention than before and has formed a topic for spirited speeches by legislators, government functionaries at all levels, the academia and private individuals (Ofomata, 1978). In Nigeria, it is believed and proven that southeastern parts of the country has the greatest number of gully erosion. It has bedeviled the region and this gave rise to the establishment of NEWMAP (Nigeria Erosion and Watershed Management Project). NEWMAP is a project aimed at reducing vulnerability to soil erosion in targeted sub-watersheds in Nigeria. It is a multi-sectoral and multi-scale project that uses an integrated watershed management approach to address environmental sustainability.

Generally, the growing interest in studying gully erosion reflects the need to increase our knowledge on its impacts and controlling factors that vary under a wide range of causes (Nwajide and Hoque, 1979), and this has led to the development of numerous stochastic and process-based models, with increasing emphasis on the use of the Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Satellite Remote Sensing (SRS). Remote sensing technology is massively deployed in the study of natural hazards of which gully erosion is part of them. There are numerous works carried out with respect to gully erosion. Iro et al (2022) in studying gully erosion in Urualla used Landsat imageries that spanned for a period of 16 years. A total of 16 Landsat imageries for 16 years, were classified according to landuse and landcover system in the study. Okereke et al. (2012) in their study of gully erosion in Okigwe southeastern Nigeria made use of Landsat TM data. The aim of the study was to integrate the remote sensing data of the study area, identify the drainage and lineament patterns/trends and their relationship and contribution to the development of gully erosion in the study area. In applying Satellite Remote Sensing and GIS Tools in the study of gully erosion, Amanbagara et al. (2015) made use of Spot-5 imagery in their acquisition of satellite data. The aim of the desk study is to review the capabilities of various remote sensing technologies in the study of natural hazards studies and gully erosion in particular.

THE APPLICATION OF REMOTE SENSING TO IDENTIFY AND STUDY GULLY EROSION HAZARD

There are numerous sensors that are used in the acquisition of environmental data for onward study of gully erosion menace. Remote sensing technology plays an indispensable driving role in soil erosion monitoring. The establishment of an erosion inversion framework driven by data and models is a crucial aspect in the integration of quantitative remote sensing and erosion monitoring, as shown in Figure 1.

Remote sensing technologies do operate within certain electromagnetic spectrums or spectral bands. So there is the need to look at the various spectrums/bands and their capabilities in natural hazards studies with particular reference to gully erosion.

Fig. 1. Soil erosion inversion model based on remote sensing technology (Source: Cuicui Ji., 2024)

Erosion features present obvious spectral reflectance differences in the different bands of remote sensing images. Satellite sensors play a crucial role in gully erosion studies, as they provide valuable information on the extent, depth, and dynamics of gully erosion.

These satellite sensors provide various data products, such as:

1. Visible (VIS) imagery., 0.4 - 0.7 micro meter: useful for
 - Detecting changes in land cover and vegetation health and density
 - Soil moisture(indirectly)
 - Gully morphology and extent
2. Near-Infrared (NIR) imagery., 0.7 - 1.3 micro meter: useful for
 - Vegetation water content and health
 - Soil moisture(indirectly)
 - Gully vegetation mapping
3. Short-Wave Infrared (SWIR) imagery., 1.3 – 3.0 micro meter: useful for
 - Soil moisture and temperature
 - Mineral mapping (e.g., clay, silt)
 - Gully erosion material identification.
4. Thermal Infrared (TIR) imagery., 3.0 – 14.0 micro meter: useful for
 - Land surface temperature
 - Soil moisture and heat flux

- Gully erosion thermal anomalies
- 5. Microwave (MW) imagery., 0.3 – 30 GHz: useful for
 - Soil moisture (active and passive)
 - Surface roughness and texture
 - Gully erosion monitoring(e.g., SMOS, AMRSR2)
- 6. L -Band (1.4 GHz) - SMOS. useful for
 - Soil moisture and ocean salinity
 - Penetrates vegetation and clouds
 - Gully erosion monitoring
- 7. C -Band (5.3 GHz) – Sentinel-1. Useful for
 - Soil moisture and surface roughness
 - Gully erosion monitoring (e.g., change detection)
 - Penetrates clouds
- 8. X-Band (9.6 GHz) – TerraSAR-X. useful for
 - High-resolution gully morphology
 - Surface roughness and texture
 - Gully erosion monitoring (e.g., change detection)
- 9. SAR data: useful for detecting changes in surface roughness and soil moisture.
- 10. DEMs (Digital Elevation Models): useful for analyzing topography and slope changes.

REMOTE SENSING CAPABILITIES.

Remote sensing exhibits various capabilities with respect to data acquisition. The capabilities include the following:

1. Wide area coverage
2. High spatial resolution
3. Frequent data acquisition
4. Cost effectiveness
5. Ability to access remote or inaccessible areas.

REMOTE SENSING TECHNOLOGIES USED IN GULLY EROSION MAPPING AND RELATED STUDIES

Several satellite sensors are well suited for gully erosion mapping, depending on the specific requirements and conditions. However, the choice of sensors depends on factors like spatial resolution, revisit time, and data availability. Often, a combination of sensors is used to leverage their strengths and provide a comprehensive understanding of hazard events. The remote sensing technologies used in gully hazard applications are grouped into four and these are:

1. SAR (SYNTHETIC APERTURE RADAR) SENSORS.

These sensors are particularly useful for natural hazards which includes gully erosion mapping due to their ability to penetrate clouds and capture data at night, making them ideal for monitoring these events in cloudy or nighttime conditions. Optical sensors are useful for identifying natural hazards mapping areas, but are limited by clouds cover and daytime requirements

➤ SENTINEL-1

Sentinel-1 is an SAR sensor and provides high resolution images (up to 5m meters) and for mapping gully morphology and extent, detecting small-scale gullies and monitoring changes in their morphologies. SAR data can be used for change detection analysis, helping to identify areas of gully erosion and deposition. Beside gully erosion it can be applied to Land and sea monitoring, natural disasters mapping, sea ice observations, ships detection. Emergency response: Flooding, landslides, volcanoes and earthquakes.

Band: The Sentinel-1 mission provides data from a dual-polarization C-band Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) instrument at 5.405GHz (C band).

Spatial Resolution: This instrument has a spatial resolution down to 5 m (16 ft) and a swath of up to 410 km (250 mi).

Temporal Resolution: Sentinel-1 satellites carry a C-band SAR instrument to provide a combined all-weather, day-and-night supply of imagery of Earth's surface every six days

Swath width: Up to 400 km (250 miles).

Revisit Time: 12 days allowing for frequent Earth's surface changes monitoring. See Table 1 below for the major characteristics of Sentinel-1

➤ **RADARSAT-2(C-band)**

Radarsat-2 is a Canada radar satellite launched in 2007, carries a synthetic aperture radar (SAR) sensor called C- band SAR. This sensor operates at a frequency of 5.4 GHz(C- band). The C-band SAR sensor provides high-resolution imagery, day and night regardless of weather conditions. It is used for monitoring gully erosion in areas with dense vegetation or cloud cover. The RADARSAT-2 satellite mission beside gully erosion monitoring capabilities offers powerful technical advancements that enhances marine surveillance, ice monitoring, disaster management (e.g., flood and earthquakes), land use/land cover mapping, environmental monitoring, resource management and mapping. Table 1 shows the major characteristics of Radarsat-2

Figure 2. Image of RADARSAT-2 Credit: ESA.

➤ **ALOS-2(L-band)**

Advanced Land Observing Satellite-2, also called Daichi-2, is a 2,120 kg Japanese satellite launched in 2014. It carries a synthetic aperture radar (SAR) sensor called PALSAR-2(Phased Array L-band Synthetic Aperture Radar-2). It operates at a frequency of 1.27 GHz (L-band). Since it does not need other sources of light such as the sun, SAR has the advantage of providing satellite images regardless day or night. It is used for gully erosion monitoring in areas of under dense vegetation or cloud cover. Other applications are Crop monitoring, Land use/Land cove mapping, Disaster management (e.g., flood, and earthquake), Maritime surveillance, Environmental monitoring (e.g., oil spills, deforestation). Table 1 below shows the major characteristics of ALOS-2

Figure 3. Image of ALOS-2(L-band)

2. OPTICAL AND INFRARED SENSORS

➤ **Landsat 8/9 (OLI)** – 30m resolution. This refers to the combined data from both Landsat 8 and 9, which shares the same Operational Land Imager (OLI) sensor. The data is a combination of both satellites, providing a robust and long term record of Earth’s surface changes. Landsat 9, like Landsat 8, has a higher imaging capacity than past Landsat, allowing more valuable data to be added to the Landsat global land archive—around 1,400 scenes per day. The Landsat 8/9 (OLI) has a higher spatial resolution (30-100 meters) and better spectral resolution than Landsat TM and ETM+, making it a popular choice for gully erosion studies.

Other applications include: Land use/land cover mapping, Disaster management (e.g., flood, fire), Climate change research, Crop monitoring, Urban planning, and Environmental monitoring. OLI is a multispectral sensor that captures images in nine spectral bands. Table 1 shows the major characteristics of Landsat 8/9 (OLI)

➤ **Sentinel-2 (MSI)** – 10-20m resolution.

As part of the Copernicus Programme, Sentinel’s fleet of 6 missions is a game changer. Specifically, Sentinel-2 is a clear upgrade to Landsat, except that it’s missing the thermal band (Copernicus). The Sentinel-2 was launched by the European Space Agency (ESA), carries a multispectral instrument (MSI). MSI is onboard both Sentinel- 2A (launched in 2015) and Sentinel-2B (launched in 2017). Sentinel-2: Sentinel-2 is a high-resolution multispectral sensor with a spatial resolution of 10-20 meters, making it suitable for detecting small-scale gullies and monitoring changes in gully morphology.

The Sentinel-2 Multi Spectral Imagery applications, the main thematic areas, focusing on four Copernicus core services, Land Monitoring, emergency management, security and climate change spatial planning, forest management, water management, agriculture and food security. MSI captures images in 13 spectral bands covering the visible, near infrared, shortwave infrared parts of the electromagnetic spectrum.

Band 1 -5: Visible light (blue, green, red, red edge and near infrared).

Band 6 - 7: Short-wave infrared (SNIR), and thermal infrared (TIR)

Band 8 -13: Short-wave infrared (SWIR). Table 1 below shows the major characteristics of Sentinel-2 (MSI)

Figure 4. Image of Sentinel-2. Credit: ESA.

- **MODIS (Terra/Aqua)** – 250-500m resolution. The Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) sensor is onboard NASA's Terra and Aqua satellites, launched in 1999 and 2002 respectively. It is useful for monitoring large scale gully erosion patterns and trends. As part of NASA's multi-talented A-Train fleet, Terra is the jack-of-all-trades. For example, ASTER models terrain, MODIS classifies land cover and MOPITT monitors air quality. Applications include: Land use/land cover mapping, Vegetation monitoring, Ocean color and temperature, Atmospheric studies (e.g., aerosols, clouds, fire detection, climate change, and flood detection research. MODIS captures images in 36 spectral bands:
Bands 1-2: Visible (0.62-0.67micrometer, (0.84- 0.87 micrometer)
Bands 3-7: Near infrared
Bands 8-14: Short-wave Infrared
Bands 15- 19: Thermal Infrared
Bands 20-36: Atmospheric and Oceanographic bands (various wavelengths). Table 1 below shows the major characteristics of MODIS (Terra/Aqua)

Figure 5 Image of MODIS Credit: ESA

- **WorldView-3/4 (VNIR)** – 1.24-1.84 Resolution. The WorldView-3 and WorldView-4 satellites, operated by Digital Globe (now part of Maxar Technologies), are equipped with a high-resolution, multispectral imaging instrument called the Panchromatic and Multispectral Imager (PAN/Multispectral). The satellites carry a multispectral sensor called the Ball Aerospace-built instrument. These high-resolution commercial satellites offer a spatial resolution of 0.31- 0.46 meters, making them ideal for detecting small-scale gullies and monitoring gully erosion at high spatial detail. Applications include: Due to their high resolution imagery and multispectral capabilities some of the applications are: Land use/land cover mapping, Environmental monitoring, Disaster response-floods, wildfires, hurricanes, Mineral exploration, Agricultural monitoring, Maritime surveillance, Climate change research, Map updating and commercial mapping, Natural resource management etc. Maxar's cutting-edge high-resolution satellite is ridiculously crisp (31 cm). Worldview imagery is so sharp that you can almost see license plates. In fact, it's the only commercial satellite that can deliver at this resolution. WorldView-3 and WorldView-4 have multispectral cameras that capture data in various bands, which are used to create color images and analyze the reflected radiation from the Earth's surface. Please note that both satellites also have hyperspectral cameras that capture data in hundreds of bands across the electromagnetic spectrum, which can be used for more detailed analysis and applications such as mineral identification, crop monitoring, and environmental monitoring. Table 1 below shows the major characteristics of the WorldView-3/4(VNIR)

Figure 6. Image of World View3/4 Credit: 2020 MAXAR.

3. HIGH RESOLUTION SENSORS

➤ **SPOT 6/7 (HRG)** – 1.5- 6 Meter Resolution

In 1986, France's SPOT-1 satellite was cutting edge. Since then, it has captured Earth's vegetation, elevation, and even the Chernobyl disaster. SPOT-6 & -7 are twin commercial Earth observation satellites operated by Airbus Defence and Space (previously as Astrium Services). The satellites carry the High-Resolution Instrument (HRI) on board. The HRI is a high-resolution camera that captures imagery in the visible and near-infrared spectrum. The SPOT 6/7 High resolution optical imagery: 1.5-6 meters resolution is suitable for detailed gully mapping and monitoring. It can be combined with other data sources like SAR or hyperspectral data for enhanced analysis. It has the capability to allow for 3D terrain modeling and gully morphology analysis. The HRG instrument is used for various other applications, including: Land cover classification, Crop monitoring, Natural disaster response Environmental monitoring, and Urban planning. Table 1 shows the major characteristics of SPOT-6/7 (HRG)

Figure 7. Image of SPOT 6/7 Credit: CNES.

4. MICROWAVE SENSORS

➤ **SMOS** (Soil Moisture and Ocean Salinity) – 35-50 km resolution

SMOS (Soil Moisture and Ocean Salinity) is an European Space Agency (ESA) satellite mission that was launched in 2009. The satellite carries a unique instrument called the Microwave Imaging Radiometer using Aperture Synthesis (MIRAS), which is designed to measure the soil moisture and ocean salinity over the global oceans. Overall, the MIRAS instrument on SMOS is a powerful tool for monitoring soil moisture and ocean salinity on a global scale, and it has been used in a variety of applications, including climate modeling, agriculture, and coastal zone management.

The MIRAS instrument is designed to measure the following parameters:

Soil moisture: MIRAS measures the soil moisture by detecting the changes in the microwave radiation that is emitted by the soil as a function of its moisture content.

MIRAS measures soil moisture levels, which is essential for understanding gully erosion processes. L-band microwave radiation: MIRAS operates at 1.4 GHz, allowing for penetration of vegetation and soil, providing accurate soil moisture data.

Ocean salinity: MIRAS measures the ocean salinity by detecting the changes in the microwave radiation that is emitted by the ocean as a function of its salt content.

The MIRAS instrument has several advantages, including:

Global coverage: MIRAS can measure soil moisture and ocean salinity over the entire globe, making it an ideal instrument for monitoring these parameters on a global scale. It enables monitoring of gully erosion worldwide.

High sensitivity: MIRAS has high sensitivity, which allows it to detect small changes in soil moisture and ocean salinity.

Low frequency: MIRAS operates at a low frequency, which makes it less affected by atmospheric interference and allows it to penetrate deeper into the soil and ocean. Table 1 shows the major characteristics of SMOS

Figure 8. Image of SMOS. Credit: ESA.

➤ **AMSR2 (Advanced Microwave Scanning Radiometer) – 5- 50km resolution.**

AMSR2 (Advanced Microwave Scanning Radiometer 2) is a passive microwave sensor that is onboard the Japanese satellite GCOM-W (Global Change Observation Mission - Water 1). It has capabilities for gully erosion studies. It has global coverage, providing global data coverage, enabling monitoring of gully erosion worldwide. AMSR2 is designed to measure various atmospheric and oceanic parameters, including:

Sea surface temperature: AMSR2 measures the sea surface temperature with a high accuracy and spatial resolution.

Sea surface wind speed: AMSR2 measures the sea surface wind speed with a high accuracy and spatial resolution.

Sea surface roughness: AMSR2 measures the sea surface roughness, which is an indicator of ocean waves and currents.

Atmospheric humidity: AMSR2 measures the atmospheric humidity, which is an important parameter for understanding climate and weather patterns.

Atmospheric temperature: AMSR2 measures the atmospheric temperature, which is an important parameter for understanding climate and weather patterns.

AMSR2 provides data on global precipitation, ocean wind speed, water vapor, sea ice concentration, brightness temperature, and soil moisture. AMSR2 NRT products are available through LANCE generally within three hours of a satellite observation. Applications include geo-science, climatology,

agriculture, pollution and disaster control, detection, reconnaissance, surveillance, and status registration in general. Table 1 shows the major characteristics of AMSR2

Table 1. Remote sensing sensors used in gully erosion studies and their characteristics.

Satellites/Sensors	Characteristics							
1. Synthetic aperture radar(sar) sensors								
	Band	Orbit	Spatial Res	Revisit Time	Swath Width	Year of Launch	Merits	Limitations
Sentine l-1	5.405GHz C- band	Sun-syn. 693 km altitude	5 m	12 Days	400 km	April 2014	Day or Night, under cloud cover	Speckle noise and Geometric distortions
Radars at-2	5.4 GHz(C-band)	Sun-Syn. 795 km	10m -100m	About 3 Days	500 km	December 2007	Under cloud, High vegetation	computational expense
ALOS-2	1.27 GHz (L-band)	Sun syn 628 km	Up to 1m (3m spotlight mode)	14 Days	Up to 70 km(50km spotlight mode)	May 2014	Enhanced data processing capabilities	Cannot detect Open-water flooding
2. Optical and infrared sensor :								
Landsat 8/9 (OLI)	30m (multispectral, 15m(Panchromatic band).	Sun syn.	30 m	Every 16 Days	185 km	2013 and 2021	High radiometric Res.	Limited no of Acquisition dates
MODIS (Terra/Aqua)	36 spectral bands.	705 Km	250 – 500 km	1 -2 Days	2330 km	1999 and 2002	Land and Water	Cannot observe under cloud cover
World View-3/4 (VNIR)		Sun syn 617 km	1.24-1.84 m Resolution	1-4.5 Days	13.1 and 18.5 km each	2014 , 2016	High Agility	Not recommended for lower plant coverage
Sentine l-2 (MSI)	13 Spectral Bands	Sun syn 786 km	10 – 20 m	Every 5 Days	290 km	2015	cloud-free imagery, detailed cloud detection	Atmospheric correction, no thermal infrared band
3. High-resolution sensors:								
Spot 6/7 (HRG)		Sun Syn 694 km	1.5-6 m	2 -3 Days	60 km (HRI) mode 120 km (HRS)	2012, 2014	High geometric accuracy	Atmospheric effect and Radiometric noise
4. Microwave sensors								
SMOS	(L-band: 1.4 GHz, 21 cm)	Sun Syn	35 – 50 km	1 – 3 Days	1000 km	2009	Exact forecasting	the antennas size, L-Band

							of weather and disastrous events	instrument is technologically challenging
AMSR 2		Sun Syn 699.6 km	5 – 50 km	1.- 2 Days	1450km – 3200km	May 18, 2012	Generates extensive suites of intercalibrated products	Radiometric calibration errors, Noise and bias in the data.

CONCLUSION.

Remote sensing has proved invaluable to study of diverse phenomena on the surface of the earth. It has various applications ranging from communication, navigation, mineral exploration, natural resources management, environmental monitoring, disaster monitoring and management and a host of others. In this desk top study applications of remote sensing technologies were discussed. There are various types of satellites that can be deployed to study flood and gully erosion hazards and some of them were discussed. We looked at the satellites sensor types, applications, electromagnetic spectrum covered (band), spatial resolutions, year of satellite launch, revisit time, life span, orbit and limitations/disadvantages

REFERENCES

- Cuicui Ji, Yiming Cao, Xiaosong Li, Xiangjun, Pei., Bin Sun., Xuemei, Yang., and Wei Zhou.(2024). A review of the satellite remote sensing techniques for assessment of runoff and sediment in soil erosion. *Scienco, Journal of Hydrology and Hydromechanics.* 72, 2024, 2, 252–267
- Iro, S., Duru, P. N, and Achalonu C. A (2022) The use of Remote Sensing and GIS Methodology in the Analysis of Urualla Gully Erosion site Imo State Nigeria. *J Environ Sci Curr Res* 5: 030.
- JSTOR. (1968). Urban Gully Erosion in USSR Soviet Studies. 19(3):426-429.
- Kakembo V, Xanga W.W. and Rowntree K. (2010). Topographic thresholds in gully development on the hillslopes of communal areas in Ngqushwa Local Municipality, Eastern Cape, South Africa. *Catchment Research Group Rhodes University, S/Africa; 2010.*
- Kalu, A.O. (1995). Soil erosion and landslide: 21st century environmental issues and challenges to rural development in Nigeria. Department of Urban and Regional Planning, Abia State University, Uturu, Abia State. MURP, unpublished seminar paper in Waugh; 1995.
- Nwajide C. S. and Hoque M. (1979). Gullying processes in South eastern Nigeria. *The Nigerian Field.* Vol. 44(2):64-74.
- Ofomata GEK (2002) *Geology in Ofomata (ed). A survey of the Igbo Nation Africa.* Onitsha: FEP.
- Okereke, C.N., Onu, N.N., Akaolisa, C.Z., Ikoru, D.O., Ibeneme, S.I., Ubechu, B., Chinemelu, E.S. and Amadikwa, L.O. (2012). Mapping Gully Erosion Using Remote Sensing Technique: A Case Study of Okigwe Area, Southeastern Nigeria. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Applications*
- Poesen J. W, Vandaele K, and Van Wesmael B. (1996). Contribution of gully erosion to sediment production on cultivated lands and rangelands. *Erosion and Sediment Yield: Global and Regional Perspectives (Proceedings of the Exeter Symposium July).* IAHS Publ. no. 236;